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Impact of land-use changes on soil health and greenhouse gas emissions [ILUC-SH-GHGE]

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Introduction and motivation

High global population growth requires increasing food production, which may lead to exhaustion of soils as the primary resources for crop growing, in a business as usual scenario. Therefore, it is necessary to find sustainable solutions for securing food supply, avoiding land degradation and minimizing the greenhouse gasses emission from agricultural fields. One option may be the introduction of temporary or ley grasslands into cropping cycle, which is hypothesized to preserve soil organic matter and to avoid nutrient leaching. So far scientists studied the effect of grassland introduction into cropping cycles on the quantity and properties of soil organic matter (Crème et al., 2018), on allocation of C within soil aggregates (Panettieri et al., 2017), soil biogeochemical parameters (e.g. composition and dynamics of cutin and suberin) (Armas-Herrera et al., 2016) and GHG fluxes from soil (Abdala et al., 2014). However, these studies often are focused on one ecosystem compartment, while the processes occurring in terrestrial ecosystems are always related to the interactions of the three domains - Earth solids, Biosphere and Atmosphere.

Therefore, the aim of our the project was studying the functions of microorganisms (Biosphere) and their efficiency (Earth solids) as drivers for GHG emissions (Biosphere & Atmosphere), and linking of parameters related to two compartments (Earth solids, Biosphere) to the CO₂ and N₂O emissions in the field conditions (Atmosphere).

Scientific objectives

The main objective of the study was to elucidate the impact of land-use changes on soil „health“ and GHG emissions by studying:

- the dynamics of quantitative and qualitative evolution of soil organic matter (SOM) under land-use changes (Earth solids);
- the microbial dynamics and functioning in relation to the land-use changes (Biosphere);
- microbial enzyme activities related to carbon, nitrogen and phosphorous cycles and their indirect impact on GHG emission (Biosphere and Atmosphere).

Overall, the proposed project aims combining the data from several domains and their interactions in order to generate new knowledge on both, the agricultural and environmental effect of grassland introduction into cropping cycle as an example of land-use changes. Considering only one of them will lead to imbalance in social needs for food and safe environment.

Methodology and experimental set-up

The experimental site is the long-term observatory on environmental research called “Agrosystems biochemical cycles and biodiversity” (SOERE-ACBB) situated near Lusignan at the INRA research station in the southwest of France.

The treatments of the long-term field experiment (since 2005) were the following (tabl.1): 1) Temporary grassland (6 years grassland and 3 years of crops) without N fertilization (TG-N); 2) Temporary grassland with N fertilization (TG+N); 3): Permanent grassland (PG); 4) Continuous cropping system - permanent maize plot (CC-M); 5) Bare soil – no vegetation (BS).

Table 1. Experiment design of selected treatments at the study site of SOARE ACBB

	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
CC	Maize	Wheat	Barley	Maize	Wheat	Barley	Maize	Wheat	Barley	Maize	Wheat	Barley	Maize	Wheat
TG-N	Grassland -N						Maize	Wheat	Barley	Grassland -N				
TG+N	Grassland +N						Maize	Wheat	Barley	Grassland +N				
PG	Grassland													
BS	Bare soil, no vegetation													

The top 10 cm of soil were sampled in June 2018 from each plot (5 treatments X 4 randomized blocks). At least five soil cores were randomly taken from each plot and a composite sample was prepared. Soil samples were passed through a 2 mm sieve and subdivided for different analysis: 1) fresh soil (kept at 4 °C) for enzyme assay, C and N in microbial biomass and incubation experiment and 2) dry soil for total C and N, and ¹³C and ¹⁵N analysis.

Field chambers for CO₂ and N₂O emissions measurement were installed at 4 and 6 sampling points in TG+N and PG treatments respectively after sampling had been done.

Enzyme kinetics were assayed using fluorogenically labeled substrates based on 4-methylumbelliferone (MUF) for phosphatase, chitinase, β-glucosidase. Enzyme kinetics modeling has been done with ModelMaker modeling software.

Microbial biomass C and N was determined by the chloroform fumigation-extraction method. Dissolved organic carbon (DOC) and nitrogen (DON) were measured from unfumigated samples.

The total carbon (C), nitrogen (N) and stable isotopes (¹³C and ¹⁵N) content of soil measured in a single analysis in dry samples using a CHN autoanalyser (CHN NA 1500, Carlo Erba) coupled with an isotope ratio mass spectrometer (Optima, Elementar).

A five day Incubation experiment was carried out to measure basal respiration of fresh soil. Briefly, 1 mL of 1 M NaOH was placed into the incubation jar with 25 g of soil adjusted with water to 40% of WHC. The traps were replaced on the second and the fifth days of the experiment. Inorganic carbon was measured in the NaOH traps by TOC analyser (Schimadzu).

Before statistical analysis the Nalimov test was done to identify outliers. A one-way ANOVA and posthoc Fisher test were conducted for all parameters measured in our experiment.

Preliminary results and conclusions

The effect of land-use change was significant at p<0.01 level for all parameters except the MBC to MBN ratio (Fig 1j). The goal treatments were TG-N and TG+N, where grassland introduced into cropping cycle. Therefore, we calculated the percentage of increase/decrease for values at other land-use type comparing to TG-N. Thus, total C (fig 1a) and total N (fig 1b) increased in TG+N and in PG, but decreased at CC-M and BS. The C/N ratio (fig 1i) was maintained at TG+N and PG, but decreased significantly by 6-9% at CC-M and BS.

The Δ¹³C (fig 1c) decreased in PG, but increased in CC-M and BS. Thus, soil under maize and bare soil was more ¹³C enriched. The increasing in Δ¹⁵N values (fig 1d) for CC-M and BS indicate higher N turnover, suggesting that the N-cycle becomes more open here and that N losses as N₂O emission or ¹⁵NO₃ leaching may have occurred.

DOC (fig 1e) and DON (fig 1f) increased or did not change after changing land-use. Importantly, DON for CC-M increased approximately 2.5-folds. Despite the considerable higher values (71-80%) for DON in PG and TG+N, the increase was not significant if compared to TG-N.

The fluctuation of MBC (fig 1g) and MBN (fig 1h) data across the different land-use changes were in line with total C and N in our experiment. However, there was no significant difference for MBC/MBN ratio (fig 1j).

The field GHG gasses emission can be estimated about one year after measurement. Meanwhile, based on the data from incubation experiment (fig 2 a and b) basal microbial respiration remained similar or slightly decreased for TG+N, significantly increased for 50 and 43% for PG and decreased for CC-M and BS by about 56-76% respectively. That could indicate that microbiological processes are hampered in CC-M and BS, and exacerbated microbial activity at PG. The results of incubation experiment can not be considered as data on Atmosphere. Therefore, to judge about the influence of land-use changes on Atmosphere the data on CO₂ and N₂O measurements in field should be considered upon availability (approximately at end of 2019).

Figure 1. The content of total C (a) and N (b) and their ratio (i), $\delta^{13}\text{C}/^{12}\text{C}$ (c) and $\delta^{15}\text{N}/^{14}\text{N}$ (d), dissolved organic carbon (DOC) (e) and organic nitrogen (DON) (f), microbial biomass carbon (MBC) (g) and nitrogen (MBN) (h) and their ratio (MBC/MBN) (j) under five land-use practices*. Data are presented as mean values ($n=4$, except $n=6$ for PG) and standard errors in brackets. For each column different letters indicate significant differences ($p<0.05$). * TG-N - temporary grassland without N fertilization; TG+N - temporary grassland with N fertilization; PG - permanent grassland; CC-M - Continuous cropping system - permanent maize plot; BS - bare soil.

Figure 2. Basal microbial respiration (a) and Basal microbial respiration rate (b) in soils under five land-use practices*. Data are presented as mean values ($n=4$, except $n=6$ for PG) and standard errors in brackets. For each column different letters indicate significant differences ($p<0.05$). * TG-N - temporary grassland without N fertilization; TG+N - temporary grassland with N fertilization; PG - permanent grassland; CC-M - Continuous cropping system - permanent maize plot; BS - bare soil.

Figure 3. The maximal activity (V_{max}) of B-glucosidase (a), chitinase (b) and phosphatase (c) in soils under five land-use practices*. Data are presented as mean values ($n=4$, except $n=6$ for PG) and standard errors in brackets. For each column different letters indicate significant differences ($p<0.05$). * TG-N - temporary grassland without N fertilization; TG+N - temporary grassland with N fertilization; PG - permanent grassland; CC-M - Continuous cropping system - permanent maize plot; BS - bare soil.

The maximal activity of enzymes (V_{max}) showed a similar trend across land use practices for β -glucosidase (fig 3a) and phosphatase (fig 3c). The changes in V_{max} values for these enzymes at different

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land-use types were in accordance to those obtained for total C, total N, MBC and MBN. However, V_{max} for chitinase (fig 3b) was the highest at the initial land use type (TG_N) and only decreased in all others. That calls to consider the N losses at CC-M and BS, where chitinase V_{max} decreased by 31 and 80% respectively.

Thus, based on the preliminary results it is reasonable to suggest that introduction of 6-years grassland (fertilized or unfertilized) into cropping cycles could maintain the microbial biomass and its activity at the levels close to permanent grassland. However, three years cropping interruption significantly reduced total C and N content if compared to 9 years continuous grassland.

Multidisciplinary approach

The combination of data on CO₂ emission (Atmosphere) with the amount of microbial biomass, enzyme activity (Biosphere) and the content of C and N (Solid Earth) in the soil allow to access the land use changes more complex. Furthermore, this interdisciplinary approach will help to take into account global warming potential of different land use practices, possibility for carbon sequestration and ability to supply crops with nutrients.

Outcome and future studies

The obtaining results will be valuable for the experts in land management and help them better understand the possible positive and negative issues of land-use changes, as there is always a trade-off between agronomical and environmental considerations. Future studies are needed to conduct similar experiments at contrast climatic zones to take into account temperature and precipitation effect.

References

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Principal investigator

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to be 'N. Bilyera'.

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